

Culture and Sensitivity Patterns in Surgical Site Infections at Government General Hospital, Nizamabad: A Prospective StudyT. Spandana¹, K. Darahasa², Syeda Amtul Moqueeth³, R. Shiva Kumar⁴¹Senior Resident, Department of Microbiology, Osmania Medical College, Telangana – 500095²Associate Professor, Department of Microbiology, Government Medical College, Nirmal, Telangana – 504106³Professor, Department of Microbiology, Government Medical College, Nizamabad, Telangana – 503001⁴Senior Resident, Department of Microbiology, Government Medical College, Nizamabad, Telangana – 503001

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Abstract:**Background:** Surgical site infection is one of the leading cause of Hospital acquired infections in developing countries. Surgical site infection rates ranges from 0.5% to 15% globally, 23% to 38% in India.⁷ Hence identification of bacterial pathogens and their antibiotic susceptibility testing is required for successful treatment of SSI.**Aim & Objectives:** To evaluate the bacterial spectrum, antibiotic sensitivity pattern and drug resistance Of isolated organisms in surgical site infections.**Materials and Methods:** Total of 110 pus samples were collected over a period of one year from surgical site infections. Detection of Organisms was done by Conventional culture and Biochemical methods, antibiotic sensitivity pattern of the isolates was studied by Kirby-bauer disc diffusion technique following CLSI guidelines.**Results:** Of the 110 clinical isolates 28 (25.45%) were pus/swab culture positive. Gram Positive organisms 15 (53.57%) were the predominant causative agents of SSI compared to Gram negative organisms 13 (46.42%) in the cases. Prevalence of MRSA is 9 (86%) of the isolated Staphylococcus aureus. ESBL production was observed in 6 (46.1%), MBL production was observed in 2(15.38%) of Gram negative isolates.**Conclusion:** The study gives an insight into bacterial pathogens and their antibiotic sensitivity patterns isolated from SSI. Preparation of antibiogram suitable for the hospital and its strict implementation is required in order to prevent antimicrobial resistance (AMR).**Keywords :** Hospital acquired infections, Surgical site infections (SSI), Antibiotic sensitivity testing.

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Introduction

- Surgical site infection is one of the leading cause of Hospital acquired infections in developing countries. [10]
- Surgical site infection ranges from 0.5% to 15% globally, studies in India have consistently shown higher rate ranging from 23% to 38%. [7]
- The Centers for Disease Control and prevention (CDC) has proposed specific criteria for the diagnosis of surgical site infection. This splits surgical site infections into three groups- superficial incisional, deep incisional and organ space infections, depending on the site and the extent of infection. [9]
- Despite recent advances in aseptic techniques including operation theatre and surgical

techniques, sterilization methods and standard protocols of preoperative preparation and antibiotic prophylaxis, SSI continues to be a major cause of hospital-acquired infections. [2]

- For proper management of the patient it is very important to find out the Pathogenic organisms which are causing the infection and also their antibiotic sensitivity patterns to start patients with appropriate antimicrobial therapy to prevent sepsis and to avoid the misuse of antibiotics so as to prevent multidrug resistant organisms in hospital settings in our efforts towards antibiotic stewardship.

Materials and Methods**Study Design**

This is a prospective study ,total of 110 samples were collected. study was carried out for one year

from March 2021 to February 2022 in the department of Microbiology after obtaining institutional ethical clearance and written informed consent from patients.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients presenting with wound infections after undergoing clean elective surgery in various surgical departments at GGH, NZB.
2. Surgical site infection occurring within 30 days after the procedure.
3. All Post operative cases from various surgical departments of all ages and both genders.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients undergoing emergency surgery.
2. Patients with contaminated or dirty surgical cases.
3. Patients with Preexisting dermatological conditions.

Pus or Wound swabs were collected under aseptic precautions by standard procedures and processed according to standard guidelines. The samples in the laboratory were processed for Direct microscopy using Gram’s staining. Aerobic cultures using Blood agar, Mac Conkeyagar were done. Organisms were further Identified by Conventional Biochemical methods.

Antibiotic sensitivity pattern of the isolates is studied by Kirby bauer disc diffusion technique following CLSI guidelines.

All the confirmed Staphylococcus aureus strains were subsequently screened for Methicillin resistance based on Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method on Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) plate using cefoxitin discs (30 µg). The isolates were considered Methicillin Resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) if the zone of inhibition was less than 21 mm and Methicillin Sensitive Staphylococcus aureus (MSSA) if it was ≥ 22 mm.

Phenotypic detection of ESBL production in Gram negative bacilli was done through disc diffusion method on Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) with Ceftazidime 30 µg in screening test and Ceftazidime 30µg; Ceftazidime-clavulanate 30/10µg in confirmatory tests. A ≥ 5 mm increase in a zone diameter around Ceftazidime-clavulanate than Ceftazidime alone was considered as ESBL producer.

Phenotypic detection of MBL production in Gram negative bacilli was done through disc diffusion method on Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) with Imipenem disc in screening test and Impipenem; Imipenem EDTA disk in confirmatory tests. The difference of ≥7 mm between the inhibition zone diameter of the IPM-EDTA disk and that of IPM only disk was considered to be MBL producer.

Method of Collection of Data

Data entry will be done using M.S. Excel and descriptive and inferential statistics using Statistical Package for social sciences (SPSS Version 21).

Result

Table 1: Distribution of culture positive and culture negative cases

Total number of cases	Number of culture positive cases	Number of culture negative cases
110	28(25.45%)	82(74.54%)

Figure 1: Shows schematic distribution of culture positive and culture negative cases

Table 2 : Sex wise distribution of cases

Total number of cases	Number of Males	Number of Females
110	63(57.27%)	47(42.72%)

Figure 2: Shows schematic sex wise distribution of cases

Table 3: Distribution of culture positive cases according to Spectrum of bacterial isolates

S. No.	Organisms	Total No.
1.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	11 (39.28%)
2.	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	6 (21.42%)
3.	CONS	2 (7.14%)
4.	<i>Enterococcus species</i>	2 (7.14%)
5.	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	3 (10.71%)
6.	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	1 (3.57%)
7.	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	1 (3.57%)
8.	<i>Citrobacter species</i>	1 (3.57%)
9.	<i>Acinetobacter species</i>	1 (3.57%)
	TOTAL	28

Figure 3: Shows schematic distribution of culture positive cases according to spectrum of bacterial isolates

Antibiotic Sensitivity Pattern Of Gram Positive Isolates

Table 4: Antibiotic sensitivity pattern of gram positive isolates

Organisms	CIP (%)	E (%)	CTR (%)	COT (%)	AMX (%)	CX (%)	DO (%)	LZ (%)
MRSA Total no.9	2(20)	3 (30)	1 (10)	2 (20)	1 (10)	-	4(40)	7 (70)
MSSA Total no.2	0	0	1 (50)	0	0	2 (100%)	0	2 (100%)
CONS Total no.2	0	0	0	1 (33.3%)	0	0	1(33.3%)	1 (33.3%)
Enterococci Total no.2	1 (33.3%)	0	1 (33.3%)	0	1(33.3%)	0	0	2 (66.6%)

CIP:Ciprofloxacin,E:Erythromycin,CTR:Ceftriaxone,COT: Cotrimoxazole,
AMX: Amoxiclav, CX: Cefoxitin, DO: Doxycycline, LZ-Linezolid

Antibiotic sensitivity pattern of gram negative isolates

Table 5: Antibiotic sensitivity pattern of gram negative isolates

Organisms	CIP	CTR	CTX	AK	CFS	PIT	MRP
Klebsiella Total no - 6	0	0	0	0	0	0	4 (57.14%)
Pseudomonas Total no - 3	2 (66.6%)	1 (33.3%)	0	3 (100%)	0	1 (33.3%)	0
E.Coli Total no - 1	0	0	0	1 (100%)	0	0	1 (100%)
Proteus Total no - 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Citrobacter Total no - 1	0	0	0	1 (100%)	0	0	0
Acinetobacter Total no - 1	0	0	0	1 (100%)	1 (100%)	1 (100%)	1 (100%)

CIP: Ciprofloxacin, CTR: Ceftriaxone, CTX: Cefotaxime, AK: Amikacin, CFS: Cefoperazone, PIT: Piptaz,
MRP: Meropenem

Phenotypic detection of MRSA

Table 6: Number of MRSA & MSSA isolates among staphylococcus aureus by cefoxitin disc diffusion.

MRSA	9
MSSA	2

MRSA: Methicillin resistant staphylococcus aureus, MSSA :Methicillin sensitive staphylococcus aureus.

Phenotypic detection of ESBL

Table 7: WSBL detection in gram negative bacteria

Number of Gram Negative Isolates	Screening Test using CAZ	Confirmatory Test using Combined Disk (CTX, CCC) & (CAZ, CAC)	ESBL Producer Or Not
13	8 were resistant to CAZ	6 isolates have increase in ZOI \geq 5mm	6 ESBL Producers

Phenotypic Detection of MBL

Table 8: MBL detection in gram negative bacteria

Number of Gram Negative Isolates	Screening Test Using Imipenem	Confirmatory Test Using Combined Disk (I, IE)	MBL Producer Or Not
13	3 were resistant to Imipenem	2 isolates have increase in ZOI \geq 7mm	2 MBL producers

Discussion

Surgical site infections are still a major cause of morbidity in the post-operative recovery period, particularly in the developing countries despite the

considerable progress in early diagnosis and treatment measures. It continues to pose a challenge to the surgeons in making a definitive clinical diagnosis and prescription of appropriate antibiotic .Hence laboratory diagnosis ,culture and

sensitivity report plays a major role.

For better survival and outcome, associated patient factors and other conditions should be considered as adjunct to the culture for early and effective wound healing/recovery with addition of

appropriate antibiotic treatment.

In the present study an attempt has been made to know the various etiological agents responsible for surgical site infections, their antibiotic susceptibility and resistance patterns.

Table 9: Comparative studies - showing culture positivity

S.No	Authors	Year	Culture Positivity
1.	Ansul Kumar et al [5]	2017 (Ranchi)	12.5%
2.	Natasha Sawhney et al [6] (2017) [4,8]	2017 (Punjab)	36.7%
3.	Seyd Mansour Razavi et al.(2015)[11]	2005 (Iran)	17.4%
4.	Gemedo Misha et.al.[1]	2021 (Ethiopia)	21.1%
5.	Present Study	2021	25.45%

Table 10: Comparative studies - showing culture isolates

Isolates	Bhargavan R et al(2018, 2012 Kerala) [4]	Bala Chandrasekhar et al. (2017, Andhra Pradesh) alallal(2017)[8]	S. Kokate et al. (2018, Maharashtra)[3]	Present Study
Staph. Aureus	19%	32%	39.72%	39.28%
Cons	-	4%	-	7.14%
E.Coli	27%	5%	21.91%	3.57%
Kleb	15%	1%	13.69%	21.42%
Proteus	8%	4%	5.47%	3.57%
Pseudo	8%	28%	5.47%	10.71%
Acinet	2%	-	8.21%	3.57%

Conclusion

Staphylococcus aureus was the commonest organism isolated, followed by Klebsiella species. The presence of MRSA,ESBL and MBL in our study calls for intensive infection control practices, and surveillance of infection is to be encouraged.

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